

Effects of Alternate High And Low Intensity Training And Progressive Training on Physical And Physiological Variables Among Boys.

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Abstract:

The aim of this study was to finding out the Effects of Alternate High And Low Intensity Training And Progressive on Training on Physical And Physiological Variables Among Boys. The purpose of the study was to explore on the effect of alternate high and low intensity training and progressive training on physical and physiological variables among boys. To achieve this purpose ninety students (N=90) were selected randomly as subjects from, Guntur District, Andhra Pradesh, India. Their age is between 16 and 18 years. The subjects were randomly divided into three groups and each group contained 30 subjects Group-I (n=30) underwent alternate high and low intensity training, group-II (n=30) underwent progressive training and group-III acted as control. The subjects were free to withdraw their consent in case they feel any discomfort during experiment and testing period. The pretest and post-test means of experimental group I, II and the control group were tested for significance by applying analysis of variance (ANOVA) after eliminating the influence of pre-test, the adjusted post-test means of experimental groups and control group were tested for significance by using analysis of co variance (ANCOVA). The level of confidence was fixed at 0.05 for significance In addition to this Schaffer's post-hoc test was employed, when the 'F' ratio of adjusted post-test means was significant to find out the paired mean difference, if any among the groups of each variable separately.

Key words: High and low Intensity Trainig and Progressive Training on Physical and Physiological

Introduction

Sports are about realizing one's potential, keeping people in sports longer are a huge gain for society. Today's world is a world of computers and spaceships. As civilization advances men's desire to compete with counterpart also increases. If he want to excel in his chosen field, the result of such desire is possible through scientific discoveries and their applications. Physical fitness is a thing which one cannot afford to neglect. The life without physical fitness is like "a ship without radar." One who is physically fit enjoys robust health and has a fine physique and satisfactory levels of social and emotional adjustments. Fitness represents the capacity to live most vigorously and effectively with one's only resources. According to Hockey (1993) physical fitness is the ability to carry out everyday task with vigor and alertness without undue fatigue and with ample energy to enjoy leisure pursuits and to meet unforeseen emergencies.

Methodology

Sample:The purpose of the study was to explore on the effect of alternate high and low intensity training and progressive training on physical and physiological variables among boys. To achieve this purpose ninety students (N=90) were selected randomly as subjects from, Guntur District, Andhra Pradesh, India. Their age is between 16 and 18 years. The subjects were randomly divided into three groups and each group contained 30 subjects Group-I (n=30) underwent alternate high and low intensity training, group-II (n=30) underwent progressive training and group-III acted as control. The subjects were free to withdraw their consent in case they feel any discomfort during experiment and testing period. However, there were no dropouts in the study and all the volunteered subjects cooperated well throughout the period of training and experimentation. A written informed consent was also obtained from the subjects.

Selection Of Variables

Independent Variables: Alternate high and low intensity training and Progressive training

Criterion Variables:

The efficiency of cardio respiratory system and physical quality is the key to success in competitive sports and games. Each sports demand have specific qualities of physical and physiological systems for top class performance hence, the following criterion variables were selected under physical and physiological variables.

I Physical variables:Speed ,Explosive power (Vertical and Horizontal) and Cardio vascular endurance

II Physiological variables:Resting heart rate,Resting respiratory rate and Blood pressure

Selection Of Tests

Even though many tests are available, the investigator has selected the standardized tests ideal for the chosen variables and most suitable for the chosen subjects for the purpose of the present study.

Table – I: List Of Criterion Variables And Their Respective Tests

Sl. No.	Name of the variable	Unit of Measures	Test/equipment
	Physical variables		
1	Speed	Seconds	50 metre dash
2	Explosive power (Horizontal) Explosive power (vertical)	Metre Centimeter	Standing broad jump Vertical jump
3	Cardio Vascular endurance	Metre	Cooper's 12 minutes run/walk
	Physiological variables		
4	Resting heart rate	Beat per minute	Automatic Blood Pressure monitor
5	Resting respiratory rate	Number per minute	Manual method
6	Blood Pressure Systolic blood pressure Diastolic blood pressure	mm. Hg mm. Hg	Automatic Blood Pressure monitor

Pilot Study:The training schedule was constructed after concluding a pilot study. For this 10 athletes were selected at random from the selected subjects. They underwent different physical activities as planned earlier. Their physical ability was assessed by the researcher along with other experts. Based on the purpose, for the subjects in the pilot study the training schedule for progressive and alternate high and low intensity training and progressive training was constructed separately. However, the individual differences were taken into consideration. The basic principles of training were followed while constructing the training program.

LOAD DYNAMICS:The intensity variations in 12 weeks of training for alternate high and low intensity training and progressive groups are given below:

TABLE – III :LOAD DYNAMICS

Weeks	Percentage of intensity	
	Alternate high and low intensity group	Progressive group
1 – 2	80	80
3 – 4	85	83
5 – 6	80	86
7 – 8	90	8 9
9 – 10	85	92
11 – 12	95	95

** Load Increase/decrease – 5% * Load increase/decrease – 3% Recovery – Partial recovery

Collection Of Data

The data on speed, explosive power (Horizontal and Vertical) cardiovascular endurance resting heart rate, resting respiratory rate and blood pressure (systolic/diastolic) were collected by administering 50 meter dash, standing broad jump, vertical jump, cooper's 12 minutes run/walk, automatic bio monitor manual method respectively. Pre-test data were collected two days before the training program and post-test data were collected two days after the training program.

Conclusions

From the results of the study the following conclusions were drawn.

1. Speed is significantly increased by alternate high and low intensity training. Further the improvement in speed is not in favour of progressive training.
2. There is no significance difference between alternate high and low intensity training and progressive training on speed.
3. Explosive power (Horizontal/Vertical) is remarkably documented in favor of alternate high and low intensity training and progressive training.
4. There is no significant difference between alternate high and low intensity training and progressive training groups on explosive power (Horizontal and Vertical)
5. Cardiovascular endurance has increased by alternate high and low intensity training and progressive training but the significant difference does not exist between training groups.
6. Resting heart rate (RHR) is significantly reduced by alternate high and low intensity training and progressive training.
7. There is no difference between training groups on RHR.
8. Resting respiratory rate (R^2) is reduced only by alternate high and low intensity training where as progressive training failed to reduce resting respiratory rate.
9. There is no significant difference between alternate high and low intensity training and progressive training on resting respiratory rate.
10. Systolic blood pressure (SBP) and diastolic blood pressure (DBP) is reduced only by the alternate high and low intensity training where as progressive training has not influenced at significant level on systolic blood pressure and diastolic blood pressure.
11. There is no difference between training groups on systolic blood pressure and diastolic blood pressure.

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